

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL HAND
WASH****Mansi ,Madhavi porwal , Rishabh Yadav , Dr. Shailesh Kumar Ghatuary*, Varsha Singh**
Shri RLT Institute of Pharmaceutical Science and Technology Ekdil (Etawah)**Article Received:** December 2022 **Accepted:** December 2022 **Published:** January 2023**Abstract:**

Hand washing correctly decreases the spread of fatal, curable infections. Even schools with minimal resources have the ability to encourage hand washing with low-cost, high-impact activities. This study assessed the effects of a group hand washing station and a hand-hygiene curriculum, two interventions used in a school-based hand washing programme. Pre- and post-intervention quantitative and open-ended surveys were given to children at one primary school in Kenya (n = 38) and one primary school in Uganda (n = 57). Each school followed the matching procedures. Pre- and post-survey paired tests showed an improvement in the students' knowledge of how to act. The importance of group hand washing stations is emphasized in the study, which supports the use of educational interventions in conjunction with built environmental interventions to encourage hand washing practices.

Keywords: Health promotion, Intervention, Hand washing, Global health, School-based health, Built Environment

Corresponding author:

Dr. Shailesh Kumar Ghatuary,
E-mail: principalsrlt171@gmail.com
Contact no. : 8319485112

QR code

Please cite this article in press Mamta Namdev et al, **Formulation And Evaluation Of Herbal Hand Wash**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2023; 10(01).

INTRODUCTION:

Hand hygiene is the most crucial precaution to take in order to stop the spread of dangerous germs and diseases because hands are the primary means of transmission for bacteria and infections. The most crucial, straightforward, and affordable method of reducing infections is hand hygiene. Microorganisms can be transmitted through the use of contaminated hands.

Two dangerous bacteria and viruses, Salmonella and E. Coli, can be carried by people, animals, or equipment and spread to food. The hands perform the majority of biological functions and are frequently exposed to a variety of materials, including soil when farming, food while preparing, touching raw or contaminated food, and personal hygiene items. Because clean hands stops the spread of germs, hand washing is typically emphasised as the single most important step in any infection control programme for preventing the transfer of microorganisms between patients.

Many chemical-based antiseptics, such as soaps that effectively prevent bacterial infections and alcohol-based hand sanitizers and other products containing chlorhexidine, have drawbacks that are detrimental to the skin. The continuous use of these products can lead to pathogen resistance as well as skin irritations. The most effective method of preventing the spread of disease is hand washing. Hand washing eliminates hazardous bacteria and readily apparent dirt.

The use of plants as a source of medicine has been passed down through the generations and is a crucial part of India's healthcare system. Anti-infective compounds can be found in abundance in plants. Plant extracts have the ability to function as antimicrobial agents against a variety of pathogenic bacteria that cause infections, diseases, and treatment resistance. The primary benefit of choosing natural sources is that they are easily accessible, inexpensive, and less harmful than chemical products.

According to WHO, Most health care-associated infections are preventable through good hand hygiene practices – cleaning hands at the right times and in the right way. Covid -19 disease outbreak occurred in 2020 and now its new variant is emerging in 2022 and washing hands is still one of the significant mode of the prevention.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Samples of *Azadirachta indica* and *Aloe barbadensis* were collected from the Shri RLT institute of Pharmaceutical Science and technology, Ekdil (Etawah). Sodium Laureth Sulfate (SLES), Coco Diethanolamide (CDEA), Cocamidopropylbetaine (CAPB), Citric acid, Pearl paste, EDTA etc.

1. Preparation of neem extract-

Fresh Neem leaves are collected and dried for few days. Dried leaves were then powdered using mortar and pestle. The powdered Neem leaves are weighed and extracted by the Soxhlet apparatus using 70 ml of ethanol and 30 ml of ethanol upto 72 cycles. Then the extract was collected.

2. Preparation of aloe vera extract-

Fresh aloe vera was collected and was kept in water for 30 minutes. Then it was scraped off by the help of knife. Then the gel was collected and filtered.

3. Formulation of herbal handwash

Sodium laureth sulfate (SLES), Coco Diethanolamide (CDEA), Cocamidopropylbetaine (CAPB), Citric acid were mixed with the help of stirrer. Then pearl paste, aloe extract and neem extract were added and mixed thoroughly. Then Distilled water was added for volume makeup and required consistency. Desired quantity of herbal oil, flavorant, colorant was added to the above formulation. The formulated hand wash gel was filled in suitable containers and stored at cool and dry place.

Table 1: Formulation of herbal hand wash gel (for 100 ml)

S.no.	Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
1	SLES	40ml	40ml	40ml	40ml	40ml
2	CDEA	3ml	2ml	5ml	3 ml	4 ml
3	CAPB	3ml	3ml	3ml	3ml	3ml
4	Aloe extract	2 ml				
5	Neem extract	6 ml				
6	PG	1.5ml	2.5ml	1.5 ml	3ml	0.5 ml
7	Table Salt	1.5 gm				
8	EDTA	0.3gm	0.3gm	0.3gm	0.3gm	0.3gm
9	FD	0.3 gm				
10	Citric acid	0.1 gm				
11	Pearl paste	7.5 ml	7.5 ml	5.5 ml	9 ml	7.5ml
12	Ionized water	Q.s.	Q.s.	Q.s.	Q.s.	Q.s.

EVALUATION:

- A)physical evaluation:-**

- Appearance:-** It was determined visually.
- PH :-** The ph was determined using digital ph meter and the ph of herbal wash was found to be 5.5-6.8 .

Curve.1 pH of Herbal Hand Wash

iii) **Colour**:- It was determined visually.

IV) **Odour** :- it was determined manually.

V) **Stability studies**:- The stability of herbal hand wash gel was carried out by storing measured amount of gel at different temperature I.e.25°C,37°C,40°C for one month.During stability studies no change in colour and no phase separation were observed in the formulated hand wash.

Curve.2 Stability of Herbal Hand Wash

Foam height:

- 1)1ml of sample of herbal hand wash taken and dispersed in 50ml distilled water.
- 2) then transferred it into 500ml stoppers measuring cylinder,volume make up to 100ml with water.
- 3) 25 stroke was given and stand till aqueous volume measured upto 100ml and measured the foam height.

Fig.2 Foam height Evaluation of Herbal Hand wash

Foam Retention: - 50ml of herbal hand wash was taken into a 250ml graduated cylinder and shaken ten times. The volume of foam at 1 minute interval for minute was recorded foam Retention should be stable at least 5 min.

Antimicrobial study:-

i) Test Microorganisms-

A panel of common pathogenic microorganisms was used in the study, which includes two gram – negative bacteria (*Klebsiella pneumonia*, and *Salmonella microorganism*).

ii) Disc-diffusion method-

Using the disc—diffusion method, the antibacterial efficacy of the herbal hand wash and extract was assessed. Using sterile cotton swabs, a suspension of the examined microorganisms was uniformly swabbed onto agar plates. Sterile blank discs were individually impregnated to the varied concentrations of formulated hand wash (100, 250 and 500 mg/ml) and were poured onto the inoculated agar plates. The plates will be inverted and incubated at 37°C for 24 h for bacteria. By measuring the diameter of the resulting zone of inhibition against the test organisms, the antibacterial activity was determined.

iii) By Gram Positive Bacteria-

1ml of sample of hand wash was dissolved in ujala solution. Then it was found that after stirring for 1 min. sample cleared the solution and killed the bacteria.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

The antimicrobial efficacy of the formulated herbal hand wash was tested on *S.mutans* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, by Disc diffusion method. The results showed that the hand wash prepared with neem extract and aloe vera extract had significant activity. The activity of herbal hand wash formulation showed significant inhibition of bacterial growth in the culture plate.

Table 2 : Physical evaluation of Formulation

S. no.	Parameter	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
1	Appearance	Clear	Clear	Clear	Clear	Clear
2	Homogeneity	Homogeneous	Homogeneous	Homogeneous	Homogeneous	Homogeneous
3.	pH	5.5- 6.8	5.5- 6.8	5.5- 6.8	5.5- 6.8	5.5- 6
4	Viscosity (m pascal)	50- 130	40- 120	50- 130	50- 130	50- 130
5	Stability	Stable	Stable	Stable	unstable	Stable
6.	Foam stability	Stable	stable	unstable	unstable	Stable
7	Foam height	12.5cm	10 cm	5 cm	2cm	11.3 cm

Table 3 : Antibacterial activity of herbal handwashe (Zone of inhibition in mm) (n=3)

Concentration (mg/ml)	<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	<i>Salmonella microorganism</i>
F1	7.34±3.5	10.54±2.4
F2	10.79± 1.3	15.88±3.5
F5	13.94± 1.43	18.67±1.3
Ciprofloxacin (5µg)	32.34± 8.69	26.89± 2.3

CONCLUSION:

The main cause of diseases affecting the skin, respiratory system, digestive tract, etc. is the hand. The bar soap becomes contaminated because of various illnesses and germs, which may cause germs to spread. The added benefit is that the soap in the liquid hand wash is unspoiled and uncontaminated. In

today's sophisticated society, liquid hand washes are used considerably more frequently than bar soap. With every fresh pump, wash your hands. There are several different hand washes on the market that all claim to eradicate dangerous bacteria quickly and effectively. It is vital to evaluate the effectiveness of handwashing in order to determine this. The

organisms identified for hand wash conducting viable count experienced an average percentage reduction and log reduction.

REFERENCES:

1. Shah MA, Natarajan SB, Gousuddin M. Formulation, evaluation, and antibacterial efficiency of herbal hand wash Gel. *Int. J. Pharm. Sci.* 2014;25(2):120-4.
2. Sandeep DS, Charyulu RN, Nayak P, Maharjan A, Ghalan I. Formulations of antimicrobial polyherbal hand wash. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology.* 2016;9(7):864-6.
3. Joshi MG, Kamat DV, Kamat SD. Evaluation of herbal handwash formulation.
4. Khanam S, Afsar Z. Herbal disinfectants: a review. *World J Pharmaceut Res.* 2013;3(1):258-73.
5. Bagade PV, Gidde ND, Nadaf SI, Desai PV, Lokhande MS, Sargar LV. Formulation and Evaluation of Gel Based Herbal Hand Wash Using Extracts of Argemone Mexicana.
6. Chitkara M, Sindhu RK, Singh I, Kumar D, Sandhu IS, Arora S. Formulation and Evaluation of Essential Oils based Liquid Herbal Hand Wash. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology.* 2020 Apr 30;13(4):1917-20.
7. Patel A, Kushwah P, Pillai S, Raghuvanshi A, Deshmukh N. Formulation and evaluation of Herbal Hand wash containing Ethanolic extract of Glycyrrhizaglabra root extract. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology.* 2017 Jan 28;10(1):55.
8. Khan AM, Raghav PK. Development and standardization of neem and aloe vera based herbal hand wash using low cost Indigenous Technology. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology.* 2021 Aug 1;14(8):4137-42.
9. Ganguly D, Banerjee1a M, Chakraborty1b A, Das1c H, Sekh1d A, Arif MD, Sarfaraj1e ST, Ghosh R, Ghosh S, Sahoo DK. PREPARATION AND EVALUATION OF POLYHERBAL HANDWASH OF DIFFERENT HERBAL SOURCES. *NEUROQUANTOLOGY.* 2022 Nov;20(11):8113-23.
10. Pallai DR, Chandrashekar SK, Nayak D, Banu A, Kumar P, Pai V, Ram AH, Raj R. Development and evaluation of Herbal hand wash with Neem Alcoholic Extract. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology.* 2021;14(1):308-10.
11. Jayant L, Snehal DJ, Chetan D, Diksha J. Formulations of herbal hand wash with potential antibacterial activity. *Int J Res Adv Tech.* 2015;2(2):11-5.